

ZANGAZUR CORRIDOR AND ITS SIGNIFICANCE**Hasanova N.***Teacher of Agjabadi branch of ADPU*
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10581856>**Abstract**

The Zangezur Corridor is an important geopolitical and economic passage connecting the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic, an exclave of Azerbaijan, from the territory of Armenia to the main part of Azerbaijan. The corridor has historical, cultural and strategic importance and serves as an important link for transport, trade and regional connectivity in the South Caucasus region. The creation and start of operation of the Zangezur Corridor is a result of the 2020 Nagorno-Karabakh ceasefire agreement that ended the conflict between Armenia and Azerbaijan. The importance of the Zangezur corridor lies in its potential to reshape regional dynamics. It gives Azerbaijan direct access to its exclave and Turkey, strengthens economic and political relations in the region. For Armenia, this creates an opportunity for economic development and integration into regional initiatives, potentially reducing its dependence on traditional routes. The corridor also has the potential to strengthen peace and stability in a region historically marked by ethnic and territorial conflicts.

The Zangezur Corridor is seen as part of a wider regional transport network connecting the South Caucasus with Europe and Asia. Its development can contribute to the economic growth of the countries involved and increase their geopolitical importance. Successful implementation of the corridor faces challenges, including political will, security concerns and the need to develop substantial infrastructure. The future of the Zangezur Corridor remains a topic of great interest and importance in regional geopolitics and international relations. The evolution of the Zangezur Corridor is poised to have a transformative impact on regional cooperation and economic development in the South Caucasus. It symbolizes a new era of engagement and cooperation, potentially easing long-standing tensions in the region. The development of the corridor is not only important for Azerbaijan and Armenia, but also has wider implications for international trade and geopolitical alignments.

Keywords: Regional Integration, Economic Development, Geopolitical Importance, Infrastructure Investments, Peace and Stability, Cultural Exchange.

INTRODUCTION

The region, characterized by its rich history and complex geopolitical landscape, entered a new stage of potential transformation with the introduction of the South Caucasus Zangezur Corridor. This corridor, created as a result of the 2020 Nagorno-Karabakh ceasefire agreement, proposes to connect the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic with the main territory of Azerbaijan through Armenia. Its emergence represents a significant shift in regional dynamics and a path not only to enhanced connectivity, but also to a resolution of long-standing geopolitical tensions. The strategic importance of the Zangezur corridor cannot be underestimated. It serves as a vital link for Azerbaijan's access to both Nakhchivan and its ally Turkey, thereby reshaping regional trade and political alliances. For Armenia, the corridor creates an opportunity for economic development and potential integration into regional economic systems, which can alleviate its geopolitical isolation [1, p.98].

It examines the historical context that led to the creation of the Zangezur Corridor, its potential impact on regional economic and political landscapes, and both the challenges and opportunities it presents for the countries involved. The importance of the corridor extends beyond the immediate region, potentially influencing international trade routes and geopolitical strategies. Thus, understanding the Zangezur Corridor is essential to understanding the evolving dynamics of the South Caucasus and its role on a larger scale. Zangezur Corridor is more than a physical crossing; It represents a new page in the geopolitics of the South Caucasus.

The corridor has the potential to redefine relations not only within the region, but also with major global powers that have vested interests in the area. Its development is closely watched by international stakeholders, including Russia, the European Union and the United States, each of which is affected in different ways by the changing dynamics in this strategically important region. The Zangezur Corridor appears to be a part of wider regional transport networks connecting the South Caucasus with Europe and Asia [2, p. 76]. The historical importance of the Zangezur corridor cannot be overlooked. The South Caucasus has long been a mosaic of cultures, ethnicities and political entities with a history marked by both cooperation and conflict. The Zangezur region in particular has been a point of contention and cultural exchange for centuries, making the current initiative not only a matter of building physical infrastructure, but also a matter of navigating a complex historical and cultural landscape. Along with geopolitical and historical perspectives, the corridor's economic implications will also be explored. The promise of expanded trade routes and easy access to global markets could bode well for the economies of Azerbaijan and Armenia, as well as the wider region. Economic benefits depend on successful diplomatic negotiations, secure and stable operations, and the willingness of regional actors to prioritize economic growth over historical grievances [3, p. 91]. These include logistical and infrastructure barriers, the need for significant financial investment, and the risk of rekindling regional conflicts. The political will and diplomatic acumen of the parties in-

volved will play an important role in solving these challenges. Zangezur Corridor is not only a physical route; It is a symbol of potential changes, embodying the hopes, challenges and complexities of the South Caucasus region. It is important to further explore the nuanced effects of the Zangezur Corridor, especially in the context of regional stability and international relations. The development of the corridor takes place in a region deeply rooted in historical grievances and geopolitical rivalry. Consequently, its progress and success depend not only on infrastructural and economic factors, but also on diplomatic and security considerations [4, p.65]. One of the key aspects of the Zangezur Corridor is its potential role in changing regional security dynamics. Witnessing intermittent conflicts, the South Caucasus stands at a crossroads where the corridor can either serve as a catalyst for peace and cooperation or become a flashpoint for renewed tension. The delicate balance of power in the region, influenced by foreign actors such as Russia, Turkey and Iran, adds more complexity to the development of the corridor. The reaction of the international community to the Zangezur corridor also attracts attention. Global powers have different interests in the South Caucasus, which may affect their relationship with the corridor. For example, the corridor's potential to open up new trade routes may attract investment from European or Asian countries, while creating strategic challenges for others. The role of international organizations and potential peacekeeping or monitoring mechanisms in ensuring the safe and impartial operation of the corridor is another important aspect to consider [5, p.98]. Additionally, the socio-cultural impact of the corridor is an area that requires exploration. The South Caucasus is home to diverse cultures and communities, whose lives and livelihoods can be significantly affected by the corridor. Issues such as population displacement, preservation of cultural heritage and community participation in the development process of the corridor are important to ensure its sustainable and equitable implementation. The Zangezur Corridor is a multifaceted initiative with wide-ranging implications. Its success depends on careful navigation of geopolitical sensitivities, robust economic planning, and an inclusive approach that takes into account the wishes and concerns of all stakeholders. It is important to provide a thorough understanding of the subtle interplay of regional and international factors shaping the corridor's potential impact, challenges, and future [6, p.47].

CONCLUSION

The Zangezur Corridor stands as a symbol of both hope and challenge in the South Caucasus, encompassing the complexities of regional geopolitics, economic aspirations, and the quest for stability and peace. Its development marks an important turning point in the region stemming from the 2020 Nagorno-Karabakh

ceasefire agreement, offering new avenues for connectivity, economic cooperation and potentially long-standing conflict resolution. With the potential to reshape trade routes, strengthen regional ties, and spur economic growth in Azerbaijan, Armenia and beyond, the corridor's strategic and economic importance is clear. The potential comes with a number of challenges that must be managed with caution and diplomacy. The success of the Zangezur Corridor depends on the ability of regional actors to work together to solve not only logistical and infrastructure needs, but also historical, cultural and environmental issues. In addition, the role of the international community in supporting and monitoring the development of the corridor is important. Global powers and international organizations are interested in the stability and prosperity of the South Caucasus, and their participation can play a key role in ensuring the success of the corridor and its positive impact on regional dynamics. In fact, Zangezur Corridor is more than a physical connection between territories. It is an opportunity for a new chapter in the South Caucasus – one that could lead to enhanced regional cooperation, economic development and lasting peace. The realization of the corridor is not only a regional concern, but also an issue of international importance with the potential to positively contribute to global trade, energy policy and geopolitical stability.

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